

ARTS

MODERN APPROACHES TO DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF DESTRUCTIVE PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN

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Abstract

Destructive pneumonia (DP) is inflammation of the lung tissue, accompanied by the development of purulent-inflammatory processes and the appearance of gross morphological changes in the lung parenchyma. Currently, acute destructive pneumonia, accompanied by various complications, is considered one of the most severe purulent-septic diseases in children. The relevance of the problem is due to the fact that, despite modern achievements in pulmonological science, the frequency of purulent-septic processes in the lungs and pleura among children of different ages continues to remain at a high level. The presented article provides extensive information about the epidemiological and etiological aspects, pathogenesis, pathomorphology and clinical signs of destructive pneumonia, as well as an assessment of the effectiveness of diagnostic methods used to clarify the diagnosis, as well as the results of recent scientific research. about various methods of antibacterial therapy and disease prevention.

Keywords: children, destructive pneumonia, diagnosis, treatment, prevention.

Introduction. Destructive pneumonia (DP), which can be caused by different strains of different microorganisms, is characterized by destructive changes in lung tissue. Currently, acute DP, accompanied by complications, is considered a dangerous and severe purulent-septic disease of childhood. In many cases, bronchopulmonary diseases that begin in childhood, especially DP, lead to disability in terms of certain diagnostic and treatment difficulties. The mortality rate of DP is 2–4%, and cases of chronic inflammation are sometimes observed [1]. For these reasons, destructive pneumonia continues to be a pressing problem for pediatricians and pediatric surgeons today. Acute DP, considered an unusual and dangerous complication of pneumonia in children, is characterized by the formation of parenchymal cavities in the lungs and destruction of the pleura, often accompanied by empyema and bronchopleural swollen tissues.

Epidemiology. In many countries using the conjugate vaccine against pneumococcal infection, despite a relative decrease (<1%) in the incidence of pneumonia and, accordingly, complications, an increase in the incidence of pleural empyema among children aged 2–4 years was noted. in the USA (1996-1998 - 3.7 cases per 100,000 children in 2005-2007; 10.3 cases in 2005-2007). Even in many states, the prevalence of empyema has increased to 5–12.5 cases per 100,000 children, due to the fact that some pneumococcal serotypes are not included in the vaccine [3–11]. Such complex variability of the epidemiological status is explained, first of all, by the variability of the etiological agent, including some temporary changes occurring in the body, as well as the use of antibiotic therapy according to the usual template regimen.

Etiology. As mentioned above, the most common pathogens of DP are pneumococci and *Staphylococcus aureus* [7-8]. Pneumococci have a polysaccharide capsule, cell surface and cell wall proteins, as well as virulence factors such as pneumolysin, the most important

of which is a polysaccharide. -read- capsule counts. There are different variants of it, causing the presence of more than 98 serotypes that can protect the microorganism from the influence of the immune system. Individual serotypes differ in their ability to colonize and cause local or general changes, as well as in resistance to antibiotics. Most pneumococcal serotypes associated with pneumococcal DP are not included in the 7-valent pneumococcal vaccine. Among them, serotypes 3 and 19 A are more closely associated with DP of pneumococcal origin. While serotype 3, which has a very dense capsule, resists phagocytosis and causes a pronounced inflammatory response including intense neutrophil infiltration with necrosis, serotype 19A, which has a high invasive potential, can grow more vigorously than other pneumococcal serotypes under normal sterile conditions and often resistant to many antibiotics and resistant to action [7]. *S. aureus* pathogens, capable of colonizing and evading the immune response, possess numerous virulence factors, including surface proteins that disrupt local defenses. When infected with *S. aureus*, after local defense is disrupted, the pathogen's toxin, which quickly destroys granulocytes and monocytes, causes infiltration of the lung tissue. On the other hand, by disrupting epithelial barriers and the immune function of cells, it facilitates the invasion of the pathogen into tissues [8-16]. Panton-Valentine leukocidin (*PVL-Panton-Valentine leukocidin*) is considered the most important of the generally recognized causes of DP, associated with severe forms of pneumonia in healthy children and adults [5-12]. The exotoxin produced by PVL first activates immune cells such as neutrophils and then destroys them, releasing foreign proteins that damage surrounding tissue. According to studies by French researchers, mortality in DP caused by PVL-secreting strains of *S. aureus* in children and adults reaches 56%, and antibiotic therapy in the form of monotherapy may be ineffective in 20% of patients [12]. However, it should be noted that the contribution

of pathogenicity of PVL-producing strains is difficult to determine. This is partly due to the fact that PVL has cell and species specificity, which manifests itself differently in individual cell cultures and experimental models. For example, human and rabbit neutrophils are highly sensitive to PVL in vitro, whereas monkey and mouse neutrophils are highly resistant to this effect. Moreover, although there is a strong association between PVL-producing *S. aureus* strains and skin and soft tissue infections in systematic reviews, no such correlation with pneumonia has been observed. Studies in adults suggest that viruses play a minor role in the development of DP. They can rarely act as a separate cause of DP, even in patients with severe adenoviral pneumonia. However, although there are few studies on the association of the disease with respiratory viruses, some reports have suggested an association of DP with RSV (respiratory syncytial virus) and influenza viruses. Thus, in a study conducted on 57 patients with pneumonia, respiratory viruses (rhinovirus, n=5; influenza, n=4; parainfluenza, n=2; coronavirus NL63, n=) were detected in the upper respiratory tract of 12 (21%) patients using PCR testing [16]. According to the results of another study, a virus culture (influenza, n=3; adenovirus + enterovirus, n=1; parainfluenza n=1, metapneumovirus, n=1) was found in 6 patients with hemolytic-uremic syndrome among 18 patients with pneumonia [10 - 16]. The mechanism of mutual association of viruses and bacteria in the respiratory tract is a multifaceted, complex and difficult to understand process. Thus, viruses have the ability to disrupt epithelial barrier and mucosal function, modulate immune function and interfere with immune system components, and reduce bacterial clearance by reducing phagocytosis and intracellular uptake of neutrophils and causing apoptosis. However, it should be remembered that no matter how difficult it is to study such an interaction, conducting this research is considered more important for the development of preventive social health strategies, diagnosis and treatment optimization.

Microbiological diagnostics. To determine the etiological causes of DP, a wide range of diagnostic tests are used (peripheral blood analysis, serological tests to detect pathogens such as *M. pneumoniae*, pleural fluid analysis, PCR, rapid antigen analysis, etc.). Among these studies, the study of pleural fluid using more sensitive molecular diagnostic methods has greater diagnostic value in order to reduce microbial culture. Pleural fluid can be collected during chest drainage, puncture, or thoracoscopy. Considering the presence of a pathogen such as pneumococci in a healthy child, sputum culture for the purpose of microbiological diagnosis is considered unreliable. Likewise, detection of viruses in the respiratory tract may not significantly influence the treatment plan (eg, stopping antibiotics). Thus, the detection of secreted viruses does not provide grounds for concluding that they are etiological agents [10]. However, one should not lose sight of the fact that the majority of patients (44–100%) were taking antibacterial drugs before hospitalization. Thus, it has already been established that positive laboratory test results can decrease by up to 64% after taking antibiotics. In such cases, it is considered more appropriate

to study pleural fluid using more sensitive tests, such as PCR [2-13]. Thus, some diagnostic difficulties associated with previous antibacterial therapy can be overcome using methods such as PCR.

Antibacterial therapy. Considering the above, the spectrum of antibacterial drugs used as first-line drugs in the treatment of DP should cover many gram(+) microorganisms, especially pneumococci, *S. aureus* and *S. pyogenes*. For this purpose, penicillin and ampicillin are the first choice drugs for severe but uncomplicated domestic pneumonia requiring hospitalization. Sometimes adding β -lactam antistaphylococcal antibiotics, such as oxacillin or flucloxacillin, to the treatment plan further improves the outcome [2-11]. It should be noted that the use of vancomycin in such patients is ineffective (it penetrates poorly into the lung parenchyma). Considering that the results of such empirical treatment are positive only in 8-55% of cases, the subsequent treatment regimen can be adjusted based on the results of laboratory tests and an antibacterial drug can be prescribed depending on the specific pathogen.

Thus, the use of β -lactam antistaphylococcal antibiotics is more effective and advisable in the treatment regimen for DP until laboratory identification of the pathogen. Although evidence is lacking, adding drugs such as linezolid, clindamycin, or rifampicin that have the ability to inhibit protein synthesis to the treatment regimen for DP caused by certain strains of *S. aureus* and *S. pyogenes* may increase the effectiveness of treatment. M. When DP develops against the background of pneumonia, it is preferable to use macrolides (clarithromycin or azithromycin) [2-15]. Type B.N. In children not vaccinated against influenza (Hib), or with nosocomial infections, empirical antibiotic therapy can be started with third or fourth generation cephalosporins. The optimal duration of antibiotic therapy in the treatment of DP has not been fully determined. However, in many studies this period varies between 13-42 days (average 28 days) [15]. During treatment, a decrease in body temperature to subnormal or normal values after 24 hours, as well as the absence of signs of sepsis in the patient and a dynamic decrease in inflammatory markers serve as a reasonable basis for transferring the antibiotic to oral administration. Instead of intravenous or intramuscular injection. However, from this point on, antibiotic therapy should be continued for at least 10–14 days [11].

Prevention. More serious attention should be paid to preventive measures among children under 5 years of age, where household pneumonia is more common. Despite recent advances in medicine, the incidence of DP caused by pneumococci, especially their serotypes not included in the pneumococcal vaccine, has been increasing in recent decades. For this reason, it is recommended to strictly monitor such issues as improving living conditions, changing indoor air, providing clean drinking water, maintaining personal hygiene and nutrition, as well as expanding the level of medical care provided to children and vaccination [8-10].

Result. Considering the above, we can conclude that the main causative agent of DP, which is consid-

ered a dangerous complication of pneumonia in children, is *S. pneumoniae* and *S. aureus*. The persistence of high fever and symptoms of respiratory failure against the background of appropriate antibiotic therapy in a patient with pneumonia suggests DP. In such cases, first of all, it is considered important to correctly assess the interaction between the host and the pathogen, clarify the microbiological diagnosis, and also optimize conservative and surgical treatment.

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